

RAMONES

Radioactivity Monitoring in Ocean Ecosystems

Deliverable

Document ID: D1.4 3rd Instrument Release, Testing in Relevant Environment

30/06/2023

RAMONES funded by European Union under Horizon 2020 FET Proactive programme via grant agreement No.101017808

Document Info

Project Information			
Acronym	RAMONES		
Name	Radioactivity Monitoring in Ocean Ecosystems		
Start Date	1 Jan 2021	End Date	31 Dec 2024
Program	H2020-EU.1.2.2. - FET Proactive		
Call ID	H2020-FETPROACT-2020-2	Topic	FETPROACT-EIC-08-2020 - Environmental Intelligence
Grant No	101017808	Instrument	RIA
Document Information			
Document Id	D1.4		
Document Title	3 rd Instrument Release, Testing in Relevant Environment		
Due Date	30-Jun-2023	Delivery Date	30-Sep-2023
Lead Beneficiary	PLOA (6)		
Beneficiaries (part.)	NKUA (1), IST-ID (2), EVOL (3), NTUA (5), PLOA (6)		
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Work packages	WP1 - Design and Develop Novel Underwater Gamma Radiation Instruments		
Version	v1.0 rev1	Stage	Final
Distribution	Public		
Keywords	Pathfinder, EIC, FET, Radioactivity, Environmental	Type	Report

	Intelligence, Underwater Research, Architecture, γ - radiation, spectrometers, Slocum gliders		
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Document Change Record

Version	Date	Change Description	Editor
0.1	20/07/2023	Initial draft and PLOA contribution	PLOA
0.2	30/07/2023	NTUA contribution	NTUA
0.3	04/08/2023	IST-ID contribution	IST-ID
0.4	26/09/2023	NKUA contribution	NKUA
0.5	27/09/2023	Final draft sent to the reviewers	PLOA
0.6	28/09/2023	Final version sent to the consortium	PLOA
0.7	07/03/2024	Revisions after reviewers' request (revision sections are greyed highlighted)	NKUA NTUA
0.8	08/03/2024	Updated and sent to the consortium	PLOA

Disclaimer

RAMONES is a European Innovation Council (EIC) FET Proactive project in the Environmental Intelligence Scope B, related to radically novel approaches to resilient, reliable and environmentally responsible in-situ monitoring, funded by European Union under Horizon 2020 FET proactive programme, via grant agreement No. 101017808.

RAMONES project's main objective is to close the current marine radioactivity under-sampling gap and foster new interdisciplinary research in ocean ecosystems. RAMONES will invest a significant effort to provide tools to enable long-term data acquisition missions, rapid deployments, low cost per information byte, and propose new AI and Robotics-driven and supported methodologies, being ambitious to eventually offer scaled-up solutions to researchers, policy makers and communities. All these may be achieved by combining state-of-the-art (SoA) methodologies and equipment from various disciplines in a well-balanced synergy, and designing new and effective methodologies targeting the marine environment, which will provide efficient response to existing natural and man-made hazards, and shape future policies for the global population. RAMONES will additionally contribute to shaping a blueprint on Environmental Intelligence in the EU and worldwide.

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List of acronyms

Acronym	Description
α SPECT	Underwater Alpha Spectrometer
CHERI	Cherenkov Imager
CTD	Conductivity, Temperature and Pressure Sensor
CZT	Cadmium Zinc Telluride
GASPAR	Gamma Spectrometer for Marine Radioactivity Studies
HPGe	High-Purity Germanium
NUV	Near Ultraviolet
ROV	Remote Operated Vehicle
SIMBLA	Simulation of Detectors and Benthic Laboratory
SoA	State of the Art
SUGI	Submarine Gamma Imager

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Abstract

RAMONES develops a new fleet of instruments to perform continuous and in situ measurements of natural and artificial radioactivity in the marine environment as part of its main objectives. Functional prototypes of the instruments are being developed, optimized, and validated in the lab, considering specific functional characteristics, optimizing integrated solutions, and fine-tuning the overall architecture. Initial field tests of two of the built prototypes have been performed during the field experiments in Milos island and Kolumbo underwater volcano, Santorini Greece.

Three types of RAMONES instruments, namely GASPAR, γ -Sniffers and SUGI, are built for the detection and monitoring of gamma radiation. The first two focus on detection and spectroscopy, while SUGI offers gamma radiation imaging capabilities, providing information for the direction of the detected events, via Compton imaging or other collimation solutions.

α SPECT implements a novel and innovative solution for the underwater detection of alpha particles, based on a radon progeny collector and a gas ingestion subsystem. CHERI, on the other hand, aims to detect Cherenkov radiation in underwater environments via task-specific, highly sensitive camera systems.

Regarding the platforms on which the instruments will be integrated on, a benthic laboratory is developed with the ability to host any combination of the RAMONES instruments, while special mounting solutions are developed for mounting γ -Sniffers on underwater gliders for scanning the water column for gamma radiation. All RAMONES instruments can also be mounted on ROVs, offering easier relocation to regions of suspected activity.

This report describes the current state of development of the RAMONES instruments.

1 Introduction

1.1 Context

This report is deliverable D1.4 “*3rd Instrument Release, Testing in Relevant Environment*” of the H2020 RAMONES project. The report is mainly a product of the work performed in all tasks of WP1 “*Design and Develop Novel Underwater Gamma Radiation Instruments*” and as the project is at its third year and the sensors are integrated to the robotic vehicles, it merges also with the WP2 “*Autonomous Marine Robotics for Collaborative Radioactivity Mapping*”.

1.2 Contents and Rationale

The main purpose of this document is to present the instruments being designed, developed and tested for all seafloor, water-column and sea surface radioactivity measurements and mapping operations. The document presents the developed instruments in their current functional form and discusses their overall integration into a common scheme, considering aspects pertaining to the platforms on which they will be mounted.

The document functions as the main reference regarding RAMONES instrumentation for every member of the consortium to extract details on the targeted specifications, operational characteristics and integration properties and standards, establishing a framework for the team to effectively carry out all the project activities which directly or indirectly depend on the instrument design and the specifications. Moreover, it drives innovation in instrumentation development and designs optimizing for efficient deployment in an autonomous, synergetic scheme during the RAMONES lifetime.

1.3 Milos field experiments

Field operations were held in Milos shallow water hydrothermal fields on 24 - 30 of March 2023. These included:

- Engineering tests for two γ -Sniffers, SUGI, CHERI UV camera, and the control unit of Benthic Lab that have been developed in RAMONES.
- Sampling from different areas for establishing background radiation levels.
- Concurrent in water measurements with the RAMONES instruments and physical sampling (gas & sediment) for laboratory measurements, for helping characterize the instruments.

Main goal of this field campaign was to establish the levels of activity, to determine if sensors are sensitive for a full-fledged deployment that is useful for monitoring of a natural system, or if technology needs development to decrease detection levels, and/or to adapt the strategy of monitoring.

It was the first big field experiment for RAMONES where all the relevant partners for this field work were present; NKUA, IST-ID, NTUA, PLOA and UCA were onsite, and ENS on remote calls. A full report will be presented with the upcoming D3.2 Coastal-water sites experiments deliverable.

1.4 Synergies with project SANTORY

Project SANTORY «SANTORini seafloor's observatorY» aims to monitor the Kolumbo volcanic chain and how the regional tectonics affect or control its activity. Additionally, by using state-of-the-art equipment, SANTORY investigates how the volcano, and its physicochemical hydrothermal processes impact the surrounding environment and the threats that imposes to the nearby communities that yearly attract thousands of tourists. A volcanic observatory consists of several sensors has been deployed on the floor of the crater, collecting physical and chemical parameters of the active hydrothermal field of Kolumbo including acoustic data, CO₂, H₂S, O₂, pressure, EC, pH and turbidity, while special thermometers were placed at specific points to measure the high temperature of the field (~230 C), current meters and visual recording of the active part of the chimneys. SANTORY is funded by the Hellenic Foundation for Research and Innovation and coordinated by Dr. Paraskevi Nomikou (Department of Geology and Geoenvironment, NKUA).

Due to the MoU between SANTORY and RAMONES, partners from NTUA and PLOA were able to participate in a field cruise at Kolumbo underwater volcano, Santorini, Greece, organized by SANTORY at no ship/ROV time cost for RAMONES. The objective of the cruise was to deploy SANTORY instruments at the hydrothermal fields with the use of the light work class ROV *Max Rover* from Hellenic Centre of Marine Research (HCMR). With that opportunity, a set of RAMONES instruments (Benthic Lab control unit, γ -Sniffer, and SUGI) were installed on the ROV and performed the first engineering tests and data collection at 500 meters depth, at the environment that is planned to execute the final RAMONES demonstrations.

1.5 RAMONES Instrumentation and Development Status

Benthic Laboratory

A functional prototype of the control unit and the powering subsystem of the benthic laboratory has been developed and tested in a natural hydrothermal environment, in Milos island and in Kolumbo underwater volcano, Santorini, Greece.

γ -Sniffers

γ -Sniffers are in a very mature state and are fully functional. The detector module has been chosen and procured (RITEC μ SPEC4000) and, based on this solution, their underwater housing design and manufacturing has been completed, passing all the stages from initial design, simulations, refinement, machining and final assembly. Dedicated software has been developed based on the ROS middleware for configuring and collecting data from the instrument. The three γ -Sniffers have been calibrated and thoroughly tested in a lab environment, both in the air and in the water, and relevant minimum detection activities have been identified. Initial tests and data from the natural hydrothermal environment have been performed in Milos island and in Kolumbo underwater volcano, Santorini, Greece.

GASPAR

GASPAR is in pending procurement phase and as such there is no field activity to report. A basic CAD has been provided and further details have been requested from the manufacturer, based also on the simulations that have been performed for various

geometries and scenarios. At the time of this report, a delivery is expected by the end of 2023.

SUGI

SUGI is in a mature state. The detector subsystem, including a high voltage module, has been chosen and procured (IDEAS GDS-100). Regarding SUGI underwater housing, both a dedicated solution and one integrated with the benthic laboratory have been developed and tested both in the lab, as well as in field operations in Milos and Kolumbo. A dedicated Python API has been developed based on the detector subsystem communication protocol for configuring the system and data logging.

α SPECT

The design of the instrument has progressed, with the radon progeny collector subsystem being finalized. A prototype apparatus of the gas ingestion subsystem has been developed and currently is under testing. The detection chamber has been constructed via 3D printing (see Section 6 below for details). Supporting electronics (e.g. amplifiers, signal processing etc.) are also being tested in the lab for quality control and optimisation.

CHERI

Two complementary solutions for the sensing unit of the CHERI instrument are being developed. One is based on a high-resolution high-sensitivity UV camera, and the other on a single photon camera. The single photon camera (SPC3 from Micro Photon Devices) has been tested during the demo period in which the camera has been kindly provided by the manufacturer. The SPC3-based solution is currently halted due to delays in the sensor procurement. The UV camera has been developed and has been tested in a lab environment.

1.6 Structure of the document

Section 2 discusses simulations related to instrument development (SIMBLA); Section 3 presents the development status of the Benthic laboratory. Section 4 to 7 present the current status of each of the RAMONES instruments, namely, γ -Sniffers, SUGI, α SPECT and CHERI. Section 8 presents the integration of the USBL/modems and γ -Sniffer sensor to the glider and Section 9 concludes the document.

2 SIMBLA - SIMulations of detectors and development of the Benthic Laboratory (Task 1.2)

2.1 GASPAR simulations

The CERN developed GEANT4 Monte Carlo suite was employed to provide detailed simulations of GASPAR based on the initially provided design by the manufacturer. The focus is on the crystal geometry and orientation inside the housing. A sample visualization of the design in Figure 1 below.

Figure 1. Simulated geometry of GASPAR (left). Note that different colors were used only for visual purposes and not indicative of difference in the material. Simulated geometry of GASPAR with the HPGe crystal being visible (right).

In the next stage, the marine environment was included in the realistic simulation, including seawater conditions (density of 1.023343 g/cm³) surrounding the sensor and the seabed (100% composition of Silicon Dioxide) at a distance of 20 cm from its front window (detector end cap). To examine GASPAR's response, a volume source (partly spherical, see Fig. 2) was simulated with its center at the middle of the detector's front window. Our main goals were:

- to calculate the maximum effective volume of detection in water to carry on with calculations of efficiency
- to estimate the minimum detectable activity,
- and to perform simulated scenarios of radioactive sources lying or buried under the seabed.

Figure 2. (left) A realistic GASPAR setup as simulated with GEANT4. (right) Same setup, with the radioactivity distribution acting as volume source (indicated with the yellow arrow).

Recently, the complete design of GASPAR was provided by the manufacturer allowing for detailed simulation of the instrument's geometry (see Fig.3). The energy resolution of the sensor was introduced in the simulation, by adding information from the manufacturer.

Fig.3 Orthogonal view of GASPAR in solid mode visualization.

As mentioned above, the first simulations' scope was to evaluate the sensor's effective detection range by evaluating only the contribution of γ -rays emitted by the seawater. Moving on to more details on the geometry, an aluminum housing was created with 4 mm thickness. The housing was cylindrical with a hemispherical dome end-cap. By

considering the dimensions of GASPAR's largest component, a housing of 6 inches inner diameter was preferred (see Fig. 4).

Fig.4 Orthogonal view of GASPAR inside the underwater housing in wireframe mode visualization.

Again, a realistic marine environment was simulated including the water volume and the seabed. In contrast to the first approximation, the distance from the housing's tip up to the seabed was decreased to 10 cm.

Fig.5 Perspective view of the entire geometry, including the world (dark blue), the effective source of seawater (light blue), the seabed (brown) and GASPAR (red) in wireframe mode visualization.

As can be seen in Fig. 5 a partially spherical volume water source was applied (light blue color) on the simulation, acting as an isotropic volume source of γ -rays. The methodology followed for estimating the detection range of GASPARG is the following:

1. At first the isotopes of interest in the marine environment had to be determined. To that extent we concluded on choosing 40K, the full decay chain of 238U as well as a progeny of 232Th which was 208Tl.
2. Simulations (implementing 109 events) were initiated by setting the source emitting γ -rays of 1460.82 keV corresponding to the decay of 40K.
3. The concept included various simulations by increasing the radius of the source (20 cm up to 160 cm) and consequently calculating the net area of the peak. It should be stressed that raw data delivered by the simulations' output were normalized, to ensure during each source's radius examined, a fixed activity concentration of 300 Bq/L in the entire source volume and a fixed data acquisition time of 3600 s.
4. To evaluate the source radius during which the response of the sensor reaches its plateau, we calculated the difference in the net peak area between successive radii studied. The strategy behind this analysis is to define the distance from the sensor from which γ -rays with the specific energy no longer contribute to the corresponding photopeak formation.

Results obtained for the γ -ray of 40K are presented in the following figure. Our conclusion is that the detection range in the seawater for the specific γ -ray can be attributed to a distance of 65 ± 5 cm since from this point on a plateau was achieved. Regarding the uncertainties of the calculated values, statistical uncertainties in the net peak area and the step from one source's radius to the next one was taken into consideration.

Fig. 6 The difference in counts of the peak area of ^{40}K between simulations with successive radii of the source as a function of the radius.

Further simulations are ongoing examining the response of GASPARG when the source is following the radioactive decay chain of ^{238}U initializing from its daughter isotope ^{226}Ra . The final goal of this series of simulations is to construct the curve of GASPARG's detection range as a function of the γ -ray energy, by covering an energy range of 0 to 3 MeV.

2.2 SUGI simulations

Simulations were performed for the submarine gamma camera (SUGI) by employing the GATE software toolkit for different scenarios inside the aquatic environment. Firstly, a detailed modeling of the detector geometry was carried out using information from the CAD drawings that the manufacturer provided us. The CZT crystal of 11x11 pixels along with its shielding was modeled in terms of dimensions and material properties, additionally considering some of the supporting electronics. The pixel electrodes for this gamma camera model are manufactured on the crystal's anode surface, while a monolithic planar electrode is crafted on the cathode surface. It is considered sufficient to simulate only one of the four CZT modules of SUGI, due to the similarity of the four modules and their independence. All simulations were carried out with 10^7 events.

The simulated results exhibit the same form (see figure 7) for both geometries, with a pixelated anode or a fully-pixelated crystal. The only difference lies in the number of detected counts. Consequently, to complete the simulations faster, all computations were performed using a fully-pixelated crystal.

Figure 7: Simulated geometry of the one CZT module of SUGI with (a) a monolithic crystal and a pixelated anode and (b) a full pixelated crystal.

Figure 8: Simulated result for ⁶⁰Co placed at the front side of the detector from (a) a monolithic crystal and a pixelated anode and (b) a full pixelated crystal.

To investigate the response of the detector a variety of scenarios were studied. The first scenario that was tested was a ⁶⁰Co point source placed at 10 cm distance away from the detector's front window inside the aquatic environment (Fig 9). From Figure 8(a), which represents the pixel number as a function of the counts, it can be observed that some pixels appear to have an increased detection intensity. More specifically, by observing the Figure 8(b), it can be noted that these pixels are the ones which are located at the outside array of the crystal.

Figure 9: Simulated geometry for a ^{60}Co source placed 10 cm away from the detector.

Figure 10: Simulated result for ^{60}Co placed at the front side of the detector. (a) Pixel number as a function of the counts, (b) Heatmap of the pixels and counts.

In the next studied scenario, the ^{60}Co point source was placed at the side of the crystal. As we can observe from Figure 12(b), the pixel array facing the source exhibits the highest signal intensity, as anticipated, owing to its greater exposure to photons emitted by the source.

Figure 11: Simulated geometry for a ^{60}Co source placed 10 cm away from the detector

Figure 12: Simulated result for ^{60}Co placed at the side of the detector. (a) Pixel number as a function of the counts, (b) Heatmap of the pixels and counts.

Next step was to study scenarios with radioactive volume sources instead of standard calibration point sources in the seabed, as well as to simulate the whole SUGI detector considering all four CZT modules.

3 Benthic Laboratory

The stationary benthic laboratory platform will host the radioactivity detectors and imaging instruments at the sea bottom for long-term, high-resolution measurements. Moreover, it will serve as a data relay point and positioning aid for the autonomous underwater gliders (AUGs).

The benthic laboratory has the capability to include all the radioactivity instruments that will be developed in RAMONES (described in the following sections), as well as, a standard conductivity, temperature, and pressure sensor (CTD), control unit, communications, and energy modules.

The development of the benthic laboratory platform is in advanced state with main achievements to be the development and testing of the control unit (hardware and software) including sensors connectivity, the energy subsystem and the procurement of deep-water flotation modules.

All the above have been tested in a real environment in the field tests of Milos and Kolumbo. They have been installed on a remote operated vehicle (ROV) that provides visual confirmation and the flexibility to efficiently survey different parts of the seabed and water column. The design of the structure of the benthic lab is in pending state as it is heavily dependent from the size of GASPARET and aSPECT instruments which are still in development.

Currently, the work is focused on the hardware and software integration of the communications and acoustic releaser systems modules from partner EVOLGICS. From the software point of view, the DMAC emulator has been used to test the acoustic modems communication, including the DMAC ROS wrapper and the following message types have been sent and received successfully using the ROS wrapper: (i) Instant Messages, with and without acknowledge with a message size up to 64 bytes, which is the maximum supported by this message type, (ii) Asynchronous Instant Messages, that allows delegating when the messages are sent to the acoustic modem based on the message timestamp and the system clock.

Binary data can also be transferred using the ROS wrapper message payload and have been validated that non-ASCII bytes can be set in the ROS wrapper message payload and they get successfully received by the receiver acoustic modem. The BURST mode has also been used, which allows to send messages with a payload larger than 64 bytes. That would be used in the future to transfer text or binary files. Next steps would be to send the gamma sniffer CPS values through the acoustic modems and multiple messages being sent simultaneously, with multiple acoustic modems. This will require a way to assign communication slots for each acoustic modem node in the network, so we can use instant messages without collisions in the channels. That would allow all nodes to efficiently communicate among them.

3.1 Field tests

The control unit with the power modules and two instruments (γ -Sniffer and SUGI) have been tested in the field operations at Milos and Kolumbo. The flexible and modular design of the system allowed it to be installed in two different remote operated

vehicles (ROVs); the small observation class ROV *METIS* (NTUA) and light work class ROV *Max Rover* (HCMR) (Figure 13).

In both field operations, the system successfully controlled and logged data from the sensors uninterrupted, providing real-time monitoring to the top-side via the ROVs' fiber optic umbilical. Moreover, we integrate to the system optical sensors and underwater Wi-Fi communication modules from the SANTORY project for helping their operations and demonstrating the open modular design of the control unit.

Figure 13: Benthic control unit, γ -Sniffer, SUGI, and UV camera installed on *METIS* ROV (left) for Milos ops and on *Max Rover* ROV (right) for Kolumbo ops.

4 γ -Sniffers (Task 1.4)

4.1 Hardware

All three pressure tolerant housings have been developed for performing initial testing of the μ SPEC4000 spectrometer with 4 cm³ CZT crystal (Figure 14). They are constructed out of hard anodized aluminum 6082-T6. One of the housings had tolerance problems from the machine shop and had to be re-machined. The overall wall thickness is 2 mm and is pressure rated for 600 m depth.

The prototypes are identical except the connection cable. One has a standard 10 m USB cable for facilitating lab and field testing with a laptop. The other two, have 2 m of underwater cable with special connectors for connecting them in the Benthic Lab, the ROV, and the Glider AUVs.

Figure 14: The complete γ -Sniffer instrument

4.2 Software

Communication with the instrument is performed either with its native MS Windows app or via a Linux driver developed inhouse by a partner. The driver is based on the robotic operating system (ROS), version Noetic and the Ubuntu 20.04 LTS. ROS is a well-defined robotic framework that is also widely used in underwater robotic and sensory systems. All the robotic platforms and instruments of RAMONES are developed using ROS which provides a common data messaging and storing framework.

The gamma sniffer ROS wrapper driver has received some minor improvements:

- Multiple acquisitions are now supported and they are more flexible:
 - “none” (default mode) allows starting and stopping sampling manually.
 - “live” and “real” allow setting up the acquisition interval.
- Support to configure more driver parameters:

- “channels”, “lld”, “uld” allow configuring the number of channels and the lower and upper channels to sample.
- “coarse_gain”, “fine_gain” allow configuring the coarse and fine gain.
- “shaping_time” allows configuring the shaping time.
- The counts per second (CPS) read by the sensor have been exposed on the State message.

The documentation has been updated accordingly in the RAMONES GitHub software repository and examples have been provided for the different acquisition modes

4.3 Field tests

γ -Sniffer was successfully tested in both field operations in Milos and Kolumbo. Two γ -Sniffer instruments and one prototype in acrylic housing were available for the experiments. One was installed together with the SUGI instrument and operated via the Benthic lab control unit, all installed on a small ROV for reaching depth and simulating vehicle approach to radioactivity sources. The other two were equipped with 10m long cable for manual operation via laptop at coastline.

4.4 ROV ops results

As shown in Figure 9, for the experiments at the island of Milos the γ -Sniffer was mounted in the front part of a portable ROV in order to measure gamma radioactivity in front of the ROV. The first two days of field work, the ROV was deployed in relatively shallow depths (3-7 meters) in the area of Paleochori beach, focusing in regions with high hydrothermal activity, manifested by distinct discolorations of the seabed and/or presence of gaseous bubbles emerging from the seabed, as can be seen in Figure 15. Different measurement scenarios were considered around those regions of interest. Mainly, measurements were taken by making the ROV sit on the seabed and taking measurement for a 3 – 5 minutes. Besides this touch-and-go strategy, measurements were also taken by making the ROV rise with a small vertical speed (<0.5 m/s) taking gamma radiation measurements in the water column at different depths. Finally, measurements were taken by horizontally traversing regions of high hydrothermal activity with small horizontal speed (<0.5 m/s). The measurements collected with the ROV-mounted γ -Sniffer in the first day of field experiments (25/03/2023) are presented in Figure 16, while Figure 17 shows the measurements collected on the 27th of March at Alykes beach. Vertical lines correspond to temporal annotations of individual measurement sessions. In Figure 17, measurements are presented for different low-level discriminator values.

Figure 15: Synchronised view of the video captured from the ROV camera during the field deployments and the counts measured by the γ -Sniffer

Figure 16: Counts measured with a sampling period of 10 sec during the first deployment of γ -Sniffer at the Paleochori beach in Milos, on the 25th of March 2023

Figure 17: Counts measured with a sampling period of 10 sec during the first deployment of γ -Sniffer at the Alykes beach in Milos, on the 27th of March 2023

Measurements were also collected during the activities of the SANTORY project at the Kolumbo underwater volcano, with the γ -Sniffer mounted on the left arm of the HCMR ROV, as shown in Figure 13. The nine ROV dives at Kolumbo were performed in two days, four on the first day and five on the second. The measurements, taken with a sampling time of 10 seconds, are shown in Figures 18 and 19 for the first and second day, respectively, in terms of counts per second. In the first dive, a high number of gamma radiation of events were recorded by the γ -Sniffer when the ROV stood on the seabed for several minutes while setting up a camera-based sensor in the proximity of a hydrothermal vent. Very high activity was also observed during the third dive at a very small distance from a hydrothermal vent. In the first four dives of the second day, the ROV did not come close to any hydrothermal vents or the seabed, resulting in relatively low CPS values. In contrast, in the last dive of the second day, several vents were visited resulting in several spikes in the CPS graph that can be observed in Figure 19.

Figure 18: Counts per second measured during four successive dives performed on the 13th of June 2023 into Kolumbo underwater volcano

Figure 19: Counts per second measured during five successive dives performed on the 14th of June 2023 into Kolumbo underwater volcano

4.5 Static ops results

During the field operation in Milos, static in-situ measurements were performed at various aquatic locations on the island. The response of the sensors was evaluated, but also data on the variation of the radioactivity levels from one area to another were acquired. It should be stressed that all the in-situ measurements will be benchmarked,

using samples of sand and sediment collected and measured in a fully-shielded HPGe detector in the lab. To conclude, the main objective of these deployments was to acquire the integrated count rate of the γ -Sniffers, under measurements with realistic environmental conditions. These integrals will feed the calibration method of the instruments. As expected the count rate achieved during these measurements was low and thus leading to short dead time values (average dead time was 0.08%). As Figure 20 (left) indicates, the most dominant component of all spectra acquired is the Compton continuum, due to intense scattering from the presence of the water and the relatively small crystal of the sensor. However, obvious differences in the Compton are observed between measurements thus justifying our initiative to monitor the total CPS recorded and make a correlation with the activity present at the measurement site. The energy range chosen for the count rate integration is from 0 to 1500 keV.

Figure 20. (left) Energy-calibrated spectra recorded while the γ -Sniffer was tested in the field at selected locations of Milos (right) a standalone measurement setup used including the γ -Sniffer encapsulated inside an aluminum housing suitable for deep-sea operation mounted on a weight to keep it steady near the seabed during operation.

The γ -sniffers have been deployed in various locations at Milos island over the period of a few days in the end of March 2023. Especially, in Paleochori Beach in south Milos, over 15 locations in and outside the water have been measured, while samples were collected from the same locations to perform high-resolution measurements in the fully-shielded HPGe spectrometer of NKUA laboratory. These high-resolution measurements are shown in Figures 21 and 22 as distribution maps of two naturally occurring isotopes, ^{228}Ra and ^{40}K . The complete set of measurement is currently under evaluation for validating the γ -Sniffers in the field (provide cps \rightarrow Bq/kg conversion coefficients for various isotopes of interests, such as those to be recorded in the Risk Information System POIS2ON, see D5.1 - D.5.3, D5.5).

Figure 21. Distribution radioactivity maps of ^{228}Ra in Paleochori Beach. Elevated activity is observed near the hydrothermal vent fields (indicated with the initials HVF).

Figure 22. Distribution radioactivity maps of ^{40}K in Paleochori Beach. Elevated activity is observed near the hydrothermal vent fields (indicated with the initials HVF).

4.6 Physical sampling methodology

Regarding the collected samples, all of them were measured in a HPGe detector of 40% efficiency and remarkable energy resolution (0.21% at 662 keV), ensuring precise measurements (figure 23). To achieve sufficient statistical data, the acquisition times extended to a minimum of 80000 s, with negligible dead time (average 0.02%). The detector, featuring coaxial geometry and a cylindrical crystal (\varnothing 60.5 mm x 63.3 mm), is shielded with lead and copper (\varnothing 52 cm, d=12 cm), making it ideal for low count rate measurements of environmental radioactivity. Prior to sample analysis, a background spectrum was obtained without any sample in the spectrometer for subsequent subtraction (Fig. 24a).

Figure 23: The fully-shielded HPGe detector used for γ -spectroscopy analysis of the samples

(c)

Figure 24: Spectra obtained from the HPGe detector, (a) background for 80000 s, (b) IAEA Reference Sample Material for 82000 s and (c) IRSN Reference sample material for 80000 s.

Identification and quantification of each spectrum line were carried out, followed by comparison with reference samples (refer to Figs 24 b and c) of identical geometry and known activity to determine the specific activities of the Milos samples. The analysis of each sample involved the use of reference samples with matching bulk geometry, including one from IAEA and one from IRSN (see Fig. 24 b and c). The IAEA reference provided specific activity values for ⁴⁰K and ¹³⁷Cs radionuclides, while the IRSN reference provided values for ²²⁶Ra and ²²⁸Ra.

The procedure for analyzing each Milos sample was as follows:

- Background correction and time normalization of both the reference and investigated samples to extract counts per second (cps).
- Cross-referencing between the reference and investigated samples by analyzing the net area rate of the photopeaks of interest, particularly for ⁴⁰K at 1460.82 keV, ²²⁶Ra at 186.21 keV, and ²²⁸Ra at 911.20 keV.
- Uncertainties in specific activity calculations were determined through error propagation across the entire process, including uncertainties from sample mass weighing, specific activity values from the reference sample supplier, and peak area calculations during spectroscopic analysis (for both reference and investigated samples).

Figure 25: Spectrum acquired from the measurement of the HVF2 sample for a total acquisition time of 80.000 sec

Figure 26: Specific activity of 40K calculated for each sample collected

Figure 27: Specific activity of 226Ra calculated for each sample collected

Figure 28: Specific activity of 228Ra calculated for each sample collected

Samples M14 and M15, both sourced from the bay of Alykes, exhibited the highest activity levels among all three radionuclides under scrutiny. Notably, the bay of Alykes prominently displayed evidence of hydrothermal activity, underscoring a potential correlation between the observed radionuclide levels and hydrothermal phenomena in the area.

4.7 Field calibration methodology of γ Sniffers

Given that the γ Sniffers will be deployed on underwater gliders moving at a set speed, it's imperative to minimize data acquisition time to maintain optimal spatial resolution for effective source identification and localization. With a glider maintaining a minimum velocity of around 20 cm/s, a 10-second integration period provides a spatial resolution of 2 m. Consequently, the short integration time underwater is expected to impact the

statistical outcomes of each measurement significantly. To address this, the γ Sniffers will not perform spectroscopy and instead rely on variations in the total count rate detected by the CdZnTe-based spectrometer. To calibrate the instruments, data from in situ measurements with handheld γ Sniffers and sample analyses using an HPGe detector in the laboratory were combined. A correlation was established between in situ measurements and sample collection conducted at the same Milos location (see to table 1).

Table 1: Pairing of in situ measurements and sample collection from the same location.

Location	Sample name	In situ measurement date
Voudia	M16	28.03.2023
Paleochori	HVF5, HVF6	29.03.2023
Agia Kiriaki	M12, M13	26.03.2023
Alykes	M14, M15	30.03.2023

Samples, ranging from 1 to 1.5 kg, were gathered and sealed for transportation to the laboratory. Following collection, all samples underwent drying at 60°C, with durations adjusted according to their water content. Subsequently, filtration was carried out using a 2 mm gravel strainer. The filtered material was then transferred into standardized 200 ml sealed PVC containers and weighed precisely. with a precision of 0.1 g. Finally, the samples were analyzed within the fully shielded HPGe detector of SERRES.

The calibration procedure can be segmented into the following steps:

- 1 Initially, the focus was on establishing a correlation between the response of the HPGe detector (measured as the integrated count rate within the energy range of 0 to 1500 keV) and the total specific activity determined for each sample, with the aid of reference samples. It's worth noting that in determining the total specific activity values, contributions from isotopes ⁴⁰K, ²²⁶Ra and ²²⁸Ra were considered. The outcomes of this correlation are depicted in Figure 29a. Subsequently, a linear regression analysis was conducted on the experimental data, represented by the red line. The equation resulting from this fitting is outlined as follows:

$$\text{Total Specific Activity} = (183.7 \pm 35.3) \times \text{CPS HPGe} + (8.1 \pm 68.7) \quad (1)$$

- 2 Following this, we proceeded to establish a correlation between the response, measured as the integrated count rate within the energy range of 0 to 1500 keV, of the two instruments: the γ Sniffer through in-situ measurements and the HPGe through sample analysis. The resulting ratios (γ Sniffer over HPGe) were then plotted against the specific activity of the corresponding sample. Employing an appropriate fit, indicated by the red line in Figure 29b, we observed no discernible dependence of the studied ratio (y-axis) on the total specific activity value (x-axis). Furthermore, the 95% confidence bands are depicted in the same figure as light green curved lines. The fitting equation is as follows:

$$\text{Ratio (Gamma Sniffer/HPGe)} = 3.02 \pm 0.41 \quad (2)$$

- 3 The final phase of calibration entails determining the relationship between the response of the γ Sniffer (total counts per second across the energy range of 0-1500 keV) and the total specific activity value. The counts per second (CPS) values for the γ Sniffer were derived using Equation 2. Figure 29c demonstrates the dispersion of the data, alongside a linear regression analysis (denoted by the red line), resulting in an equation of the following form:

$$\text{Total Specific Activity} = (60.8 \pm 11.7) \times \text{CPS Gamma Sniffer} + (8.1 \pm 68.7) \quad (3)$$

By utilizing Equation 3, it becomes possible to determine the total specific activity within the effective water column detected by the γ Sniffer through the integration of the count rate (0-1500 keV) recorded by the sensor. The rationale behind selecting the energy range (0-1500 keV) for calibrating the γ Sniffers lies in the constrained volume of the CZT crystal, which leads to reduced efficiency in detecting high-energy γ -rays.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 29: (a) The total specific activity as a function of the CPS integral (0-1500 keV) registered by the HPGe detector, the ratio of the CPS integral (0-1500 keV) registered by the γ Sniffer over the HPGe detector as a function of the total specific activity and (c) the total specific activity as a function of the CPS registered by the γ Sniffer.

5 SUGI - Submarine Gamma Imager (Task 1.5)

The Submarine Gamma Imager (SUGI) is a novel underwater γ -radiation imager. The goal of SUGI is to detect, localize and identify radioactivity in its surrounding area. The SUGI is designed to be mounted both on the benthic laboratory and ROV. When mounted on the benthic laboratory, SUGI can perform prolonged measurements from a static location, thus collecting better statistics regarding the surrounding radioactivity. On the other hand, mounting SUGI on an ROV gives the possibility of moving the instrument in the vicinity of regions of interest where significant radioactivity events are suspected. The multipurpose design of SUGI, enhances its versatility making it suitable across diverse radioactivity monitoring and mapping scenarios.

5.1 Hardware

There are no changes on the hardware from the previous report but extensive testing has indicated the updates that we will perform next:

- Dedicated housing. Currently, the SUGI sensors are housed together with the Benthic Lab control unit. The next version will have its dedicated housing that will leave space to include collimators. All the necessary hardware has been purchased and currently the new housing is under preparation.
- Isolated power system. The sensors proved to be very sensitive to electronic noise and for this reason we have already designed and tested them with their own power source which is isolated from the rest of the systems or vehicles.

5.2 Software

A custom python API has been developed for real-time (re-)configuration, system health monitoring (e.g., key component voltage, temperatures, etc.), and data readout, according to the GDS-100 TCP/UDP packet specifications (Doppio format) which uses TCP packets for system configuration and UDP packets for data readout. The developed API has been successfully tested both on x86-64 desktop/workstation systems, and on AARCH64 embedded computers, as Raspberry Pi 4. The solution allows for both online real-time processing and for off-line batch processing. Currently, processing includes reporting of total event counts and counts per second and the construction of the spectrum of the recorded events. Compton imaging functionalities are currently being developed to enable radiation imaging.

5.3 Field tests

Field test of SUGI were mostly dedicated to engineering objectives, i.e. to validate the correct operation of the instrument in its housing in a relative environment. In fact, the correct operation of SUGI, both hardware and software wise, was verified in the field operations that took place in Milos and Kolumbo. During the field operations at Milos, raw data (counts) with the SUGI instrument have been collected from the hydrothermal fields at Paleochori and Alykes. At the beginning of each test, the instrument configuration (especially detection threshold and bias) has been adjusted to make the detection counts match as good as possible the ones of the γ Sniffers. During the experiments multiple gas emitting sources (vents) have been visited with the ROV and

measurements were collected at different depths, to estimate radioactivity in the water column and on the sea bottom. Multiple radioactivity hot spots have been identified around the vents, manifested by the bubbles and the seabed discolorations (see Figure 15). Figures 30 and 31, show the rate of the events measured with the SUGI at Paleochori and Alykes beaches, respectively, in comparison with the ones measured with the γ -Sniffer. It can be observed that, apart from a small difference in scale, the measurements from both detectors are in very good agreement.

Figure 30: Comparison of the measurements taken by SUGI and the γ -Sniffer on the 26th of March at Paleochori in terms of counts per second

Figure 31: Comparison of the measurements taken by SUGI and the γ -Sniffer on the 27th of March at Alykes beach in terms of counts per second

6 α SPECT - Underwater Alpha Spectrometer (Task 1.6)

6.1 Radon Progeny Collector

The design for the detector has been finalized. It consists of a number of parts that were designed to be 3D-printable (Figs. 32, 33, 34) by commercially available 3D printers. It is designed to fit in an underwater housing with an overall length of 290 mm and 6 inches diameter, regarding the detector, while the electronics will be housed underneath. All electronics and detector modules have been procured and are currently being optimized for placement inside the housing. A gas conditioner system will also be connected to the chamber once developed.

Figure 32. A 3D CAD design of α SPECT showing the gas chamber, which will also house the supporting electronic modules (HV bias module, amplifier etc) inside a 6" diameter housing (shown as a transparent cylinder).

Figure 33. 3D printing the aSPECT modules.

Figure 34. 3D printed aSPECT modules.

The current dimensions along with some moderate estimations regarding the collection and detection efficiency provide with a sensitivity estimation (see Fig. 35). This estimation is found to be comparable to state of the art commercially available detectors. A commercially available state-of-the-art RAD7 detector will be used to

cross-validate the response of aSPECT during the various development phases, until the final release of the instrument.

3.1.2. Radon progeny collection chamber

The volume of the chamber required to achieve a C.F. of 30 Bq/m³/cpm is estimated by:

Eq.2
$$V = \frac{I}{C.F. \times r_{+} \times \epsilon_p \times \epsilon_{\alpha} \times 60 [\text{sec}]}$$

Module dimensions		Sensor sensitivity (est)	
Degrees	110	Positively charged emanated ²¹⁸ Po (r ₊)	88%
radius (dm)	0.762	Collection efficiency (ε _c)	75%
Length (dm)	3	α-particle detection eff. (<50%) (ε _α)	40%
Module volume (L)	1.50	Calibration Factor C.F. (Bq/m ³ /cpm)	20.97
2 Total sensor volume (x2) (L)	3.01	Sensitivity (10 ⁻² cpm/Bq/m ³)	4.77
		Sensitivity (cpm/kBq/m ³)	47.68
		Sensitivity (cpd/mBq/m ³)	0.07

Contents	For professional			NEW
	RAD7	Alpha Guard	CRMS10	RadonEye
Type	photodiode	ion chamber	ion chamber	ion chamber
Country	USA	German	Canada	KOREA
Sensitivity (cpm/1000Bq/m ³)	13.5	50	8.1	13.5
Minimum measuring time (h)*	0.5	0.2	1	1
Data logger	O	O	O	O
Precision(%)	±5	±3	±10	±10
Price(US\$)	9,000	18,000	5,000	250

Figure 35. Estimated design properties of aSPECT based on the currently selected geometry and operation conditions.

6.2 First αSPECT experiments

The instrument is divided into 3 modules: The gas separator/purifier, the detector module and power module. The detector setup for the radon detection module has been recently completed. A testing apparatus is currently under development with the following requirements:

- 1 It needs to be airtight
- 2 It needs to be lightproof
- 3 Conducting grounded material for noise elimination
- 4 Minimization or elimination of ground loops
- 5 Electrically isolated placement of the detector for safety

Toward this goal a metallic container is actively prepared. For the placement of the detector, an adapter was constructed designed to hold the detector, and mountable to the endcap of the final underwater housing. For the test, the adapter was mounted to the lid of the metallic container on the inside. Four PVC sheets were placed between adapter and lid to ensure electrical insulation from the high voltage.

Figure 36: The detector placed on the adapter mounted on the metallic lid. One particle detector and one preamp are currently utilized, see text for more details.

For the purposes of this test, only one precipitation chamber is utilized and therefore only one preamplifier and particle detector are needed. Feedthroughs for the HV, the preamp power and signal were drilled and will be sealed with opaque silicone. This setup will be sealed airtight, with a radium source placed inside, in order to build up radon concentration. Both the MCA and the preamplifier have non-grounding power supplies. However, the external high voltage power supply (HVPS) currently used at this stage of the experiment is grounded. Therefore, the shielding of the HV cable will not be connected anywhere. Of course, at all stages, ground connections are monitored for safety and noise elimination.

The expected outcome of this experiment is to obtain the necessary gain factors for the shaping amplifier section of the MCA to optimize the spectrum acquisition and define ROIs for the two isotopes of radon. After achieving this milestone, the next step is to implement the dedicated electronics for the detector, and specifically, gain-matching of the 2 pre-amplifiers in the analogue adder stage to obtain best resolution. After contact with the preamp manufacturers, optimal op-amps were obtained, and are ready to assemble for the latter stage. Final and exact calibration of the instrument will be performed with the use of a RAD7 detector, in a closed loop configuration, in line with the aSPECT instrument, as typically done in bibliography.

6.3 Gas separation and conditional module

A system for extracting radon gas from high pressure water has been designed and a prototype apparatus has been developed for testing the gas separation capabilities of different membranes. To perform the base design, initial development and testing, Dr. Angelos Mallios from partner PLOATECH visited his in-house consultant Dr. Richard Camilli's laboratory at Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution (WHOI), MA, US. The laboratory provides facilities and specialized equipment for the development of underwater instrumentation (Figure 37).

Figure 37. Fast prototyping facilities at Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution.

Development

The test apparatus is based on Dr. Camilli's patented high-pressure membrane attachment for underwater mass-spectrometer¹. The main components include: vacuum chamber, vacuum pump, membrane support lid, circulation pump, and a commercially available radon instrument (RadonEye). The testing concept was to test the membrane gas permeability in low vacuum conditions and the measurement of the Rn in the chamber relative to the ambient environment before proceeding with tests to higher pressure differentials.

Gas separation membranes typically are very thin and cannot support high pressure differentials, especially when a relatively large area has to be exposed to the water volume. For this initial test, a membrane with a diameter of 30 cm was chosen and a support lid was constructed by acrylic and fiberglass layers with rubber shields. A 10

¹ Camilli R. (2007). Systems and methods for analyzing underwater, subsurface and atmospheric environments. Patent # US8299424B2

mm thick acrylic lid was laser cut with 770 holes of 2.5 mm diameter for supporting the pressure differential while allowing the gas to pass through (Fig. 38). Soft fiberglass sheets were between the lid and the membrane for distributing gas from all the membrane's area. Rubber gaskets were laser cut for shielding the layers and the lid to the vacuum chamber (Fig. 39, left).

Figure 38. Laser cutting the acrylic base (left) and the rubber gaskets (right)

Lab tests

Tests were performed with a polypropylene (PP) film with the following specifications:

Thickness	0.03 mm
Structure	Biaxially Oriented
Transparency	Clear/Transparent
Size	300mm x 300mm
Density (g cm ⁻³)	0.900
Radiation resistance	Fair
Refractive index	1.490
Resistance to Ultraviolet	Poor
Water absorption - equilibrium (%)	0.03
Initial Tear Strength (g μm ⁻¹)	18 - 27
Permeability to Carbon Dioxide @25C (x10 ⁻¹³ cm ³ . cm cm ⁻² s ⁻¹ Pa ⁻¹)	6 @ 30C
Permeability to Hydrogen @25C (x10 ⁻¹³ cm ³ . cm cm ⁻² s ⁻¹ Pa ⁻¹)	30
Permeability to Nitrogen @25C (x10 ⁻¹³ cm ³ . cm cm ⁻² s ⁻¹ Pa ⁻¹)	0
Permeability to Oxygen @25C (x10 ⁻¹³ cm ³ . cm cm ⁻² s ⁻¹ Pa ⁻¹)	2 @30C
Permeability to Water @25C (x10 ⁻¹³ cm ³ . cm cm ⁻² s ⁻¹ Pa ⁻¹)	16
Permeability to Water @38C (x10 ⁻¹³ cm ³ . cm cm ⁻² s ⁻¹ Pa ⁻¹)	70

The RadonEye instrument was placed inside the vacuum chamber for measuring the Rn concentration and compared with the ambient one while a low volume pump was circulating the air between the chamber and the membrane (Fig. 39, right).

RadonEye has the following specifications:

Type	Pulsed Ion Chamber
First data out	< 60min
Data interval	10min update (60min moving average)

Sensitivity	0.5cpm/pCi/L
Operating range	10~40°C (50°F ~ 100°F), RH < 80%
Range	0.2 ~ 99.9pCi/L (7~3,700Bq/m ³)
Reproducibility	< ±10% at 10pCi/L
Accuracy	< ±10% (min. error <±0.5pCi/L)
Power	12V 1A DC adapter
Size	Φ80(mm) x 120(mm)
Weight	240g
Data communication	Bluetooth LE (Android/iOS)
Data log	max 1year (1h step)
Display	0.96 inch OLED

Figure 39. The full test apparatus (left). The RadonEye and air pump inside the chamber (right)

Three test concepts were performed: one where the membrane was exposed to the ambient air, one that was covered with water on the external side, and one that cat litter was spread over the membrane. In all cases, vacuum was pulled down to 0.5 bars and test duration was increased incrementally from 2 to 6 hours, except the one with cat litter that lasted 12 hours. In all tests, vacuum did change as well as Rn concentration inside the chamber, although cat litter increased the ambient concentration by an order of magnitude.

The above suggested that the membrane did not have enough permeability at least at this pressure differential and next steps will include testing in higher differential pressure and different types of membranes. In addition to these initial tests, new designs were sketched for deep water apparatus and prototyping material have already been ordered.

7 CHERI - Cherenkov Imager (Task 1.7)

The Cherenkov Imager (CHERI) is a novel imager for detecting Cherenkov radiation in underwater environments. Due to the low intensity of the Cherenkov radiation in most underwater scenarios, CHERI needs to have an extremely high sensitivity in the blue-violet-NUV (Near UV) spectrum, where Cherenkov has the highest intensity. Two complementary solutions have been promoted for the sensors based on which the instrument will be developed. The first is the SPC3 single photon camera from Micro Photon Devices with high photon detection efficiency and very low dark count rate. The second is a high-resolution, high-efficiency UV camera from PhotonFocus (MV4-D1280U-L01-GT). The two sensors are shown in Figure 40. The development of SUGI is based on both sensors due to their complementary nature, as one has low resolution and high pitch but can provide very accurate photon-level counts, while the other is based on a high-resolution CMOS sensor, showing high sensitivity and low-noise on the NUV spectrum.

Figure 40: SPC3 single photon camera from MPD (Left) and MV4 UV camera from PhotonFocus (right)

7.1 SPC3 camera

The SPC3-based solution development is currently halted due to delays in the sensor procurement.

7.2 UV camera

The UV camera has been developed and tested in the lab and in the Milos field operations (Figure 41). The MV4 UV camera is designed for high speed machine vision applications and for this reason it is equipped with a 10 Gigabit Ethernet interface. Due to the high acquisition rate of the camera, it requires from the networking subsystems to support “jumbo” packets which require suitable network components. In the lab network it worked as expected but there were problems connecting it via the ROVs interfaces as they didn’t support “jumbo” network packets. To overcome this limitation and to be sure that the camera will be operated in standard networking systems, an intermediate small factor PC with dual network interface will be installed between the

camera and the rest of the network. The PC and the necessary housing material have already been purchased and the integration will be performed in the next period.

Figure 41: UV camera in the lab (left) and installed at METIS ROV in Milos field work (right)

8 Glider integration (WP2 - Task 2.5)

The autonomous underwater gliders (AUGs) are the main RAMONES platforms for mapping radioactivity in the water column using the developed γ -Sniffers. In order for this task to be achieved, the gliders have to be upgraded with a robust positioning and communications system and a custom control unit. To this end, the gliders are equipped with two hydroacoustic modem units, one of them including a USBL. The USBL unit is used to position the glider with respect to the surface vehicle, whereas the other is used for communication with the fixed benthic station. A block diagram of the physical connections between the custom RPi 4 computer, glider, and modems is presented in Figure 42.

Figure 42: Block diagram of the glider internal physical connections between the γ -Sniffer sensor, Raspberry Pi 4 computer, modem-USBL, and the glider science computer. With color are the modules developed in RAMONES.

Two big milestones have been achieved in this report period: The integration of the γ -Sniffer and the preparation of the USBL/modem payload section of the glider.

8.1 γ -Sniffer integration

The γ -Sniffer integration includes the physical installation of the sensor and its electrical connection with the glider. Custom made carbon fiber brackets were developed for securing the sensor in the bow of the glider while allowing for minor repositioning on the forward axis for positioning fine tuning (Figure 43). A custom underwater USB cable was built for connecting the sensor to the RasPi 4 inside the glider.

Figure 43: Preliminary fit testing of the γ -Sniffer and the USBL/modem on the glider (left). γ -Sniffer with carbon fiber bracket installation detail (right).

8.2 USBL/modem integration

The more complicated integration is the one of the USBL/modem due to the transducers' and electronics volume, as well as its electrical requirements. For this reason, NTUA, IST-ID, and PLOA partners had predicted the need of an extended glider payload section almost from the beginning of the project and NTUA & IST-ID had proceeded with the procurements together with stiffening rings that include 2 underwater connector penetrators (Figure 44).

Figure 44: The extended glider payload section (left). The stiffening ring with underwater connectors (right).

The extended payload section increases the glider's dry volume allowing the integration of the USBL/modems electronics together with their battery bank, in addition to transducers at the external part of the cylinder (Figure 45). The dedicated battery bank provides increased energy autonomy, as well as electrical isolation with the glider's electronics for minimizing any electrical noise or interference due to modems' high energy inductive pulses. The battery bank consists of 8 Li-ion batteries

of 98 Whrs each connected in parallel, bringing the total energy capacity to 784 Whrs. A custom electronics PCB has been developed for allowing the safe parallel connection of the batteries with balanced discharge function, that also includes a remote power switch. A 3D printed chassis holds the batteries and the electronics together allowing easy hot-swapping of the batteries (Figure 46). The current state of the electronics integration to the dry compartment can be seen in Figure 47.

Figure 45: CAD model of the USBL/modem payload section.

Figure 46: Batteries 3D printed chassis with balancing and control electronics.

Figure 47: Different views of the USBL/modem electronics integration with the batteries installed.

Another task was to install the transducers on the outside part of the cylinder. Two adaptors from 1000 m depth rated syntactic foam were designed and machined. The syntactic foam adaptors are providing mechanical coupling and buoyancy compensation for the transducers' weight (Figure 48).

Figure 48: Syntactic foam adaptors. Machining and final results.

Finally, aluminum endcaps were designed, machined, and hard anodized for allowing the installation of USBL/modems underwater connectors. These endcaps were designed to replace the original ones from the gliders' science bay (Figure 49).

Figure 49: Endcap adaptors next to γ -Sniffer.

Next period tasks include: finalizing connectors installation, integrating the RasPi 4 in the science bay, ballasting the glider with the USBL/modem payload, and performing water tests.

9 Conclusions – Next stage of development

γ -Sniffers and SUGI are at a mature state of development and they have already been verified and tested in the lab and natural environment. The development of GASPAR on the other hand is delayed as its basic detection module is currently under procurement.

The design of aSPECT is at an advanced state and it is still in development. Regarding CHERI, the procurement of the Single Photon Camera is still undergoing, so the effort was given to a high-sensitive UV camera which has been tested in the lab and in the sea. The control unit of the benthic lab has been already tested in the lab, as well as in the natural environment.

Regarding the next stage of development, γ -Sniffers and USBL/modems will be fully integrated to the gliders and will be tested in the sea. Benthic lab frame will be constructed although GASPAR and aSPECT sizes are still uncertain. aSPECT gas module will be developed and tested for deep water operations. The development of SUGI will continue and together will be tested in the lab with known radiation sources. There is a possibility for RAMONES partners to participate in an upcoming SANTORY cruise in Kolumbo, Santorini where the new versions of the developed sensors can be tested in a real radioactive underwater environment.